

An Agent-Based Model of the Role of Epistemic Vigilance in Human Cooperation

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Abstract This paper uses an agent-based model with an adapted stag hunt style scenario to explore the role of the social transmission of correct information about stag hunting and potentially incorrect information about the costs of defection on cooperation in a small artificial society. The computational architecture of the model draws upon Daniel Sperber and Hugo Mercier’s concept of epistemic vigilance as well as Brian Skyrms’ work on cooperation in stag-hunt scenarios. In the model, communities of 100 hunters begin with no knowledge of stag hunting or punishment for defection and via imperfect social learning, guided by source or content vigilance, move toward a stag hunting or hare hunting equilibrium, where stag hunting may be motivated by the expectation of cooperation or by the fear of punishment. Most successful communities end up using content vigilance to determine their beliefs regarding stag hunting but use source vigilance to determine their beliefs regarding punishment, as predicted in the theoretical work of Konrad Talmont-Kaminski. These findings contribute to the ongoing debate in a variety of disciplines about the conditions under which—and the mechanisms by which—cooperation emerges and is maintained in human societies.

Keywords Agent-based model · Epistemic vigilance · Prosocial behavior · Human cooperation

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1 Introduction

Here we outline and present the initial experimental results of a computational model of the role of epistemic vigilance in human cooperation using an adapted stag hunt style scenario. The agent architectures for the artificial society are informed by the theory of epistemic vigilance originally formulated by Sperber and Mercier [3], and further articulated by Talmont-Kaminski [4], as explained in more detail below. The stag hunt game was originally proposed in [2] as a formal description of a scenario where the highest utility equilibrium requires mutual trust between the players. Inspired by a Rousseau story [1], it places two hunters in the situation of needing to independently determine whether to hunt a stag together or a hare individually. Hunting the stag offers a significantly higher payoff but requires the cooperation of the other hunter. Hunting the hare offers a guaranteed but lower payoff. The game is similar to the classic prisoner's dilemma, which becomes a stag hunt scenario if defection is punished sufficiently to lower the payoff for defection below that of reciprocated cooperation. As Skyrms has shown, providing hunters can choose whom to hunt with, the norm of cooperation typically becomes stabilised in a population of hunters [2].

In Skyrms' scenario the only unknown is whether the other player will cooperate—all the costs of the alternative strategies are known and mutually cooperating stag hunters are invariably successful. To explore the significance of knowledge regarding those variables it is necessary to draw upon epistemic vigilance theory as set out in [3]. As pointed out there, social learning makes it possible for people to benefit from the experience of others without the potential costs of obtaining that experience but at the cost of the potential for accidental or deliberate deception. To avoid this, people engage in epistemic vigilance by using cues regarding the content of the information being presented to them, as well as the source of that information to determine whether to accept it. In effect, we can consider the plausibility of what someone has told us as well as the trustworthiness of that individual in order to decide whether to believe what was said.

The choice between using content versus source vigilance has important social consequences. Talmont-Kaminski argues in [4] that, where the utility of a belief is tied to its accuracy, a preference for content vigilance will lead to better results at the social level whereas a preference for source vigilance is to be favoured where utility is not connected to accuracy. The same does not necessarily hold at the individual level. As a prime example of beliefs whose utility is not dependent upon their accuracy he proposes beliefs that motivate cooperation. This opens the way to combining the stag hunt with epistemic vigilance to empirically examine how the choice between source versus content vigilance regarding information about potential punishment and stag behaviour interacts with a repeated many-player stag hunt scenario that allows for partner choice. The results are informative regarding the potential role of the fear of supernatural punishment for motivating cooperation.

2 ABM Stag Hunting Variant

The model represents a small-scale society of a hundred hunters who initially do not cooperate, have no knowledge of how to hunt stags and have no belief in punishment regarding defection. The hunters set out in groups of five. Group of five individuals is the minimal group size that allows to introduce social cooperation to the original stag game, with eventual great reward if majority of group cooperated. Each hunter decides to cooperate either because of previous cooperation by the group members or because due to punishment they believe the utility of defection will be lower than that of an unsuccessful hunt. A minimum of three hunters must cooperate for the hunt to have any chance to be successful, its odds of success depending upon the highest stag behaviour knowledge of them. Between hunts, hunters exchange two pieces of information, one about stag behavior and the other about belief in punishment. For each piece of information, they use source or content vigilance to determine whether to accept it or not. Additionally, every ten hunt attempts, hunters evaluate their relative hunting success and whether to modify their strategy of relying upon source or content vigilance. There is no real punishment and no individual learning regarding either stag behavior or punishment beliefs.

2.1 Agent Variables

- *Competence CMP*; $CMP \in [0, 1]$ —agent's ability to perform content vigilance, i.e. judge the accuracy of beliefs. Ranges from 0 to 1—no competence to perfect competence. Generated randomly at start using uniform distribution. Does not change.
- *Status STS*; $STS \in [0, 1]$ —agent's value in considerations of source vigilance, i.e. how they and others estimate their value as source. Ranges from 0 to 1—the lowest status to the highest status. Generated randomly at start using uniform distribution. Does not change.
- *Stag beliefs SB*; $SB \in [0, 1]$ —agent's beliefs regarding stag behaviour and necessary to catch the stag. Ranges from 0 to 1—completely misleading knowledge to perfect knowledge. Starts at 0, but changes due to interactions with other agents.
- *Punishment beliefs PB*; $PB \in [0, 1]$ —agent's beliefs regarding the size of punishment for defection. Ranges from 0 to 1—completely misleading knowledge to perfect knowledge. Initially 1 for all agents, representing the perfect knowledge that there is no punishment in the model. Changes due to interactions with other agents.
- *Cooperated/Defected CD*; $CD \in \{0, 1\}$ —agent's behaviour in the previous hunt. 0 if defected, 1 if cooperated. Set after first hunt on basis of initial choice. Updated after every hunt.

- *Stag belief vigilance preference*—*SVP*; $SVP \in \{source, content\}$ —agent's preference for source or content vigilance when evaluating stag beliefs. 1 = content preferred, 0 = source preferred.
- *Punishment belief vigilance preference*—*PVP*; $PVP \in \{source, content\}$ —agent's preference for source or content vigilance when evaluating punishment beliefs. 1 = content preferred, 0 = source preferred.
- *Utility Total* *UT*—a variable representing the total utility obtained by the agent during current set of 10 hunts. Set to 0 at the start of every set of hunts and updated after every hunt. Strategies are updated each 10 hunts using the *UT* in order to identify more successful individuals and allow the less successful ones to adopt strategies from them.

2.2 Global Variables

- *Group assortment* *GA*— $GA \in [0; 1]$ —ability of cooperating agents to pick groups with cooperating agents if given the opportunity. Ranges from 0 to 1—none to complete. Determines the degree to which co-operators will group together.
- *Village size*—number of agents in the village. It remains constant at 100 agents. No deaths/births occur in the model.
- *Cooperate/defect error* *CDE*— $CDE \in [0; 1]$ —probability of agents incorrectly remembering behaviour of other agents in previous hunt. Ranges from 0 to 1—no error, to always error.
- *Strategy update group* *SUG*— $SUG \in [1; 50]$ —the percentage of agents who update their strategy regarding use of source or content vigilance. It ranges between 1 and 50 percent of the village size ($n=100$).
- *Social Learning Ratio* *SLR*— $SLR \in [0.1; 1]$ —ratio of learning beliefs (*SB* or *PB*) during *Social Learning* phase. When agents consider worthy to learn the beliefs of another agents, their beliefs moves towards that of the partner with a ratio given by *SLR*.
- *Social Learning Error*— $SLE \in [0.01; 0.30]$ —absolute value of error when learning the beliefs of another agent (*SB* or *PB*). The learning occurs during *Social Learning* phase.

2.3 ABM Cycle (Steps)

The model's flowchart is presented in Fig. 1, with the sequential steps descriptions following.

Step 1. Assignment to hunting groups. At initialization, agents are assigned into groups of five randomly. Afterwards, before each hunt agents are anew assigned into groups in the following order: Agents who defected in previous round—assigned

Fig. 1 The model flowchart and direct influences (represented with colorful arrows). Please note that Hunter (encircled in blue) represents a single agent. *Competence* and *Status* are crossed as being constant hunter properties. 5 external model parameters are to the right and denoted with circle-with-arrow symbols with arrows showing the step they affect

to a random group with free spots. Agents who cooperated in previous round—if a random number between 0 and 1 is below *GA* value, the agent is assigned to a group (when available) with free spots that contains hunters who cooperated in the previous round. Otherwise, the agent is assigned to a random group with free spots.

Step 2. Choose to cooperate/defect. In the first hunt, no agent cooperates. In later hunts, all agents determine whether they will cooperate or defect in a given hunt on the basis of:

- Expected utility of defection $XUD = -1 + (PB \times 2)$. Ranges from -1 to 1.
- Expected utility of cooperation $XUC =$ for each agent in the group (including self) add CD (with CDE being probability of misremembering own/group member CD). With CD taking a value of 1 if the agent cooperated in the previous hunt or 0 if not. If however dis-remembered (CDE fired) respectively taking the opposite value. Hence, XUC ranges from 0 to 5—none to all agents are thought to have cooperated in the previous hunt.
- Level of SB is ignored.

Step 3. Determine outcome. All defectors increase UT by 1. They caught their hare and were not punished for it as there is no punishment in the model.

All groups with less than three cooperators do not change UT . There were not enough cooperators to catch the stag.

All groups with three or more cooperators increase UT by 5 with probability equal to the highest SB among them. The group was large enough to potentially catch the stag on the basis of the best knowledge available to them.

```

if  $XUD < 0$  then
  |  $cooperate \leftarrow true$ ;      /* It is better to catch nothing than to
  | catch a rabbit and be sorely punished. */
else
  | if  $XUC < 3$  then
  | |  $cooperate \leftarrow false$ ; /* Assuming this group behaves the same
  | | as last time, there will not be enough hunters to catch
  | | the stag. */
  | else
  | |  $cooperate \leftarrow true$ ;
  | end
end

```

Algorithm 1: Choose to cooperate/defect

Step 4. Social learning. After each hunt, the villagers exchange and potentially update their beliefs. They determine whether to update their beliefs on the basis of either source or content vigilance (depending upon their preferences). In the first case, they compare their status with that of the villager they are communicating with. In the second case, they use their competence to estimate the accuracy of the beliefs in question and learn only when it seems profitable.

Each villager:

- partners up with another random villager,
- can partially adopt SB and PB from their partner, if the condition based on corresponding vigilance preference is fulfilled (as specified in details below). The degree of adopting beliefs is defined as the parameter *Social Learning Ratio* (SLR).

On the basis of their $SV P$ and PVP the villager determines whether to update their beliefs:

- If preferring source vigilance, use status (STS):
 - Calculate status difference $STSD = \text{partner's } STS - \text{Ego's } STS$
 - $STSD$ determines probability of shifting towards partner's belief with the probability ranging from 0 when $STSD = -1$; 0.5 when $STSD = 0$; and 1 when $STSD = 1$.
 - If the condition is fulfilled, own belief will be shifting towards the partner with a small $\pm$ error (the parameter *Social Learning Error*).
- If preferring content vigilance, use competence (CMP):
 - Calculate accuracy for partner's belief and ego's belief using CMP . The higher the competence, the more precise the assessment—random value if $CMP = 0$, the precise actual value if $CMP = 1$.
 - Shift towards partner's belief with $\pm$ error (the parameter *Learning Ratio Error*), if accuracy of partner's belief is estimated to be higher than of own belief.

Loop Steps one through four (from forming hunting groups to determining who cooperates, outcomes of the hunts, and social learning) are repeated in a loop ten times, allowing the agents to collect utility.

Step 5. Update strategy. After ten rounds of hunting and communicating, the agents evaluate the strategy they have been using to update their beliefs: source or content vigilance. Agents are ordered by their UT and each of those in the percentage (*SUG*) of agents with the lowest UT:

- Randomly choose between *SVP* and *PVP*
- Randomly choose an agent from those with very high UT (use *SUG* to determine size of group).
- Adopt the vigilance preference (i.e. *SVP* or *PVP*) of that agent.

Finally, all agents set their *UT* back to 0 and the cycle starts again.

Desired outcome of the game variant It is expected that over time agents will come to select stag beliefs on the basis of content vigilance and punishment beliefs on the basis of source vigilance resulting in societies dominated by highly accurate beliefs about stags and highly inaccurate beliefs about punishment. The model is specifically designed so that the two kinds of beliefs are treated exactly the same way but differences may arise because of the way the beliefs impact hunting success. This is so that any differences in source/content vigilance regarding them can be traced back to this practical difference.

2.4 The Model

The model was implemented in AnyLogic v.8.7.10. Here we present a brief description of the model. A full ODD+D protocol description can be found at the repository: <https://github.com/mrybnik/staghunters>.

3 Results

3.1 General Model Behaviour

Initial state The agent population starts with perfect knowledge of the lack of punishment in the model ($PB = 1$). The population start with no knowledge of stag behaviour ($SB=0$). The *SVP* and *PVP* strategies are varied in population, both statistically close to half *content* and *status*.

Hare hunting equilibrium The population starts with no cooperation and zeroed stag beliefs. While stag beliefs gradually increase due to learning error and then spread in the population due to social learning, cooperation initially remains low.

Fig. 2 Emerge of spontaneous cooperation. Blue area represents averaged population cooperation. Both brown and red lines are quite high, representing averaged *SB* and *PB*. Brown area presents *SVP* preferences, being mostly *source*-based. Red area presents *PVP* preferences, being mostly *content*-based. Finally green area represents averaged *Total Utility* with a quick raise from *hare hunting equilibrium* to mostly successful *stag hunting equilibrium*

Almost all hunters hunt hares and stag hunting is marginally popular. This could be called *Hare hunting equilibrium*.

Fear-induced cooperation False beliefs regarding punishment may appear due to learning error and spread due to social learning, especially with *Punishment Beliefs* learning driven by source *Vigilance Preference* (i.e. $PVP=source$). Low punishment beliefs lead to cooperation due to the fear of being punished when not cooperating, even though in reality punishment does not exist. Cooperation—once ignited with fear—spreads in population, resulting in almost all hunters cooperating in hunting stags—so called *Stag hunting equilibrium*.

Spontaneous cooperation Mistaken recall of prior cooperation (*CDE*) may lead to spontaneous cooperation, which may sometimes spread within the population resulting in the *Stag hunting equilibrium*. An example of this phenomenon is depicted in Fig. 2. The effect is enhanced by high values of *Group Assortment* parameter (*GA*).

Stag hunting equilibrium Once cooperation appears, be it due to fear or spontaneous propagation, the whole population generally cooperates all the time. This can be called *Stag hunting equilibrium*. Providing the *SB* is high enough, this results in *Utility*

Total being close to 50. In ideal conditions (perfect recall of previous cooperation $CDE=0$ and very high *Stag Beliefs*) this would result in every group hunting stags successfully.

3.2 Sensitivity Analysis: The Role of GA and CDE for Spontaneous Cooperation

A sensitivity analysis was performed using LHS hypercube sampling resulting in 10000 parameter combinations. Sampled parameters:

- *Strategy Update Group* *SUG* [0.01–0.25],
- *Social Learning Error* *SLE* [0.01–0.2],
- *Cooperate Defect Error* *CDE* [0.01–0.3],
- *Group Assortment* *GA* [0.01–1],
- *Social Learning Ratio* *SLE* [0.01–1].

Figure 3 presents the result of the analysis with percentage of cooperating agents (y-axis), level of group assortment (x-axis), different ranges of cooperation/defection error *CDE* (facets), and Vigilance Preferences (*SVP-PVP*) followed finally by the whole population (color and shape of data points).

Fig. 3 Sensitivity analysis, 4 final combinations of *SVP* and *PVP* are shown

The conclusions here are:

- Fear induced cooperation (with very high cooperation values) is visible for facets with *CDE* in range [0–0.15] and almost exclusively connected with source vigilance regarding punishment beliefs (Fig. 3: *Vigilance Preferences* **content-source** and **source-source**, blue squares and red dots)—which is necessary for false beliefs about punishment to spread.
- Villages that do not fear punishment (Fig. 3: *Vigilance Preferences* **content-source** and **source-source**, blue squares and red dots) with low values of *CDE* [0.0–0.1], regardless of *Group Assortment* value very rarely induce cooperation spontaneously. Influence of *Group Assortment* is however most visible with *CDE* in range [0.1–0.2] where it most probably helps to induce spontaneous cooperation. One can observe that raising *GA* values clearly incite cooperation in this case.
- With *CDE* over 0.3 cooperation becomes erratic for villages that apply content vigilance to both stag and punishment beliefs (Fig. 3: *Vigilance Preferences* **content-content** and **source-content**, violet crosses and green triangles), as agents cannot remember correctly who cooperated recently. This is not a problem for villages using source vigilance regarding punishment beliefs as they rely on fear-induced cooperation rather than cooperation based upon trust (Fig. 3: *Vigilance Preferences* **content-source** and **source-source**, blue squares and red dots).

3.3 The Influence of Stag Beliefs and Cooperation on Utility

Figure 4 presents the distribution of UT vs the proportion of CD in the villages for the four combinations of *Vigilance Preferences* at the end of the simulation.

Conclusions: High final *Utility Total* requires both cooperation and high stag beliefs (proficiency in stag hunting). The obvious positive correlation can be observed when content vigilance is applied to stag beliefs (facets (*SVP=content*, *PVP=source*) and (*SVP=content*, *PVP=content*) in Fig. 4), where stag hunting proficiency is learnt efficiently and therefore high. Where source vigilance regarding stag beliefs is used (facets (*SVP=source*, *PVP=source*) and (*SVP=source*, *PVP=content*), Fig. 4), however, high cooperation actually tends to worsen the population's *Utility Total*, as attempts to hunt stags are unsuccessful, due to low *SB* (hunting proficiency).

4 Discussion

The model created is complex as agents constantly change most of their properties and therefore behavior. The agents evolve through social interactions. Thus it may be seen as evolutionary model rather than a typical ABM, where agents usually behave in a constant manner. While full identification and prediction of all processes seems to be impossible, it is possible to identify and statistically confirm core authors'

Fig. 4 UT vs CD, 4 combinations of *Vigilance Preferences* at the end of the simulation

assumptions. While of course simpler model could be used, the ultimate goal is to simulate social interactions and try to understand them.

The aim of the model was to examine the role of the social transmission of potentially incorrect beliefs upon cooperation and hunting success in a stag-hunt like scenario. In the case of knowledge of stag hunting it was found to be preferable for a society to rely upon content vigilance for determining whether to accept socially transmitted information. The situation, however, was different in the case of beliefs regarding punishment for failing to cooperate with other hunters. Here, in some scenarios, it turned out to be preferable for members of a society to incorrectly believe in such punishment as it could both induce and maintain very high levels of cooperation—the necessary levels of false belief in punishment requiring a focus upon source vigilance in the case of punishment beliefs. In particular, where the chance of mis-remembering prior behaviour was low—making spontaneous cooperation unlikely—source vigilance regarding punishment beliefs helped to induce

cooperation while, where prior behaviour was often mis-remembered—leading to inconsistent trust in other hunters—source vigilance regarding punishment beliefs helped to maintain much higher steady levels of cooperation. Only for a small range of values for recall of prior behaviour and ability to use that to choose partners did levels of cooperation maintained by trust equal those maintained by the fear of nonexistent punishment.

In his study of human cooperation, Brian Skyrms assumed that cooperation was based upon accurate knowledge of the situation and rational decisions regarding expected utility. We have expanded upon his work by considering the potential effect of incorrect information passed on by social learning, driven by epistemic vigilance towards the source or content of that information. In effect, we have shown that a preference for source vigilance—while rational at the individual level—has crucial significance for the spread of incorrect information with completely different consequences at the social level depending upon whether the utility of that information being connected to its accuracy. And in the case of information that motivates cooperation, utility and accuracy can be quite separate—as proposed by Talmont-Kaminski.

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